

Material Stories: Assessing Sustainability of Digital Fabrication with Bio-Based Materials through LCA

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Abstract. Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) stands as a vital tool in gauging the environmental impacts of building endeavors. Extending LCA to emerging research practices like advanced digital manufacturing of bio-based materials becomes pivotal for refining materials, appraising outcomes, and steering architecture toward sustainable development and circularity goals. To outline the main obstacles and to provide a potential methodology, the paper presents two cases of application of LCA to digital fabrication with bio-based materials in experimental research practice. The application is framed within the ISO and EU standards for LCA and is tested through an ex-post “cradle to construction” analysis of two ERC funded projects developed by the Center for Information Technology in Architecture (CITA) at the Royal Danish Academy. Specifically, a product LCA is performed for bio-polymeric composited 3D robotic fabrication using a novel collagen-based 3D print material, and a comparative LCA is carried out for Glulam manufacturing optimization connecting data from the timbers source in the forest and sawmill with its design and fabrication. In both cases, the prototypes assembly and exhibition are covered by the analysis. The unavailability of data, difficulties in standard protocols adaptation and material and energy flows tracing in the research process emerge as the main barriers and contribute to aggravate the analysis’s uncertainty. The paper shows how to manage such uncertainties via Sensitivity Analysis to evaluate design options according to different impact scenarios. The knowledge established and the methodology outlined in this research could be useful for researchers, designers and industry in the implementation of sustainable digital fabrication processes and new construction materials.

Keywords: Life Cycle Assessment; Digital fabrication; Bio-based materials; Research-based design; Sensitivity analysis.

1 Introduction

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is an objective procedure for assessing the energy and environmental loads related to a process or activity, carried out through the identification of energy and materials used and waste released into the environment. The assessment shall cover the entire life cycle of the process or activity, including extraction and processing of raw materials, manufacture, transport, distribution, use, reuse, recycling and final disposal [1].

In its Communication on Integrated Product Policy [2] the European Commission concluded that LCA provides the best framework for assessing the potential environmental impacts in the construction industry. Following the Level(s) guidelines [3] and the European Green Deal [4], all EU countries started embracing the adoption of LCA methods. In Denmark, for instance, LCA is mandatory since 2023 for all new constructions over 1000 sqm [5]. To support designers, engineers and policy makers, LCA protocols and case studies were developed to outline how to perform environmental assessments on buildings and industrial products. Nevertheless, a relatively limited number of studies have investigated the application of LCA to novel technologies and materials, that could represent a suitable ecological alternative to current practices in the construction industry. In these cases, LCA could be pivotal to target research and communicate results [6]. Data scarcity, lack of previous research and precedents, difficulties in applying standard protocols and software are recognized as the main barriers in the application of LCA to Digital Fabrication (DF) processes and bio-based materials [7] [8]. A methodological development of LCA is necessary in order to use this instrument to evaluate and steer research and innovation projects.

This study aims to design and verify a LCA-oriented methodology for the environmental assessment of DF with bio-based materials, highlighting opportunities and limits. The methodology is framed on the ISO 14040-44 standard [9] [10] and is tested on two case studies within the ERC funded Eco-Metabolistic Architecture project, carried out at the Center for Information Technology in Architecture (CITA) at the Royal Danish Academy: Radicant and Rawlam [11-13].

Fig. 1. (a) The Radicant project by CITA, Aedes Gallery, Berlin, 2022. (b) The Rawlam prototype by CITA, Bildmuseet, Umeå, 2021 [11-13]. Courtesy of CITA.

The study investigates how LCA can have a significant impact on the decision-making processes within a research laboratory and why it should be integrated as an early-stage design step. Considering the growing popularity of DF with bio-based materials, the implementation of the here illustrated methodology could be used for the realization of environmental guidelines [18] [19] and the creation of digital databases, i.e. a “material library”, with dedicated software applications, e.g. a digital platform [20] and plug-in for computational design tools [21].

2 Background

To analyze the current trends in literature (up to 2024) about LCA application to DF with bio-based materials, a scoping review is performed via Scopus web database. The query is prompted by the following combination of keywords, joined by the Boolean operators “AND” and “OR”: “life cycle assessment” OR “LCA” OR “life-cycle assessment” AND “bio-based materials” OR “biomaterials” OR “bio-materials” AND “digital fabrication” OR “digital manufacturing” OR “advanced manufacturing” OR “additive manufacturing” OR “robotic fabrication” OR “robotic manufacturing”. The query is limited to the fields of title, abstract and keywords.

The results show how this topic is still under-investigated, as “Product Sustainability Assessment” [22] is the only paper available. In this work, authors present an overview of the 3D printing technique and the materials used for the production, discussing how LCA application at every step of the production can help in achieving sustainable development along with the additive manufacturing techniques.

This lack of literature is examined by Kohtala and Hyysal [23], who state how reports on the sustainability of personal fabrication are emerging as the phenomenon spreads, often appearing as grey literature [24]. The few empirical studies that exist mainly focus on additive manufacturing, relevant to some digital fabrication equipment used in our research, such as studies on energy consumption and Life Cycle Analyses [25] [26]. When compared to mass production processes, digital manufacturing has the potential to reduce material, waste and energy, at least for small batches [27] and may mitigate negative impacts connected to supply chains [28]. However, toxicity of especially additive manufacturing materials remains a concern [29] [30], as well as the high energy consumption of digital fabrication.

3 Materials and methods

3.1 Research methodology and assessment method

The LCA methodology is organized into 4 steps, namely: Flows; Data; Knowledge; Uncertainty.

In the “Flows” step, goal and scope of the assessment are defined and the Life-Cycle Inventory (LCI) is performed. In this phase, the objective of the whole analysis is identified, the system boundaries are taken into account and the functional unit of reference

is expressed. In the LCI, all materials included in the analysis are listed and tracked down to assess impacts, e.g. CO₂ emissions and energy consumption (modules A1-A3). For each material and each process unit, all the inputs (energy, water, resources) and outputs (waste, pollution, by-products) are examined and diagrammed.

In the “Data” step, information about the materials and the processes are collected and calculated. Data collection draw from different sources:

- The ÖKOBAUDAT generic database, a german-based platform included into the official LCA Danish software LCAByg [14] [36];
- EPD Denmark [15];
- Other EPDs or studies in literature reporting LCA according to their technological or time representativeness, since they might be referred to different geographical contexts.

The calculations performed in this study are guided by specific impacts-related questions and are performed through a spreadsheet by converting the gathered data into the functional unit and adding impacts from transportation (depending on the different vehicle data from ÖKOBAUDAT) and energy use for manufacturing and construction (referring to the energy mix 2018). Modules A1-A3 (production stage) and A4 - A5 (construction process stage) are considered. For transportation, the extraction and processing of the fuel is included. The production of the vehicle is not included in the balancing.

The “Knowledge” step corresponds to the Life-Cycle Impact Assessment – LCIA phase, in which the results are graphically explicated.

In the “Uncertainty” step a Sensitivity Analysis is performed to deal with possible inaccuracy of calculations, e.g. testing different materials or products [16] [17].

3.2 Limitations of the study

To address the goal of the study, several limits in the application of standard LCA in our research have been identified and workarounds - mainly based on assumptions - were established.

Only a few data are available about bio-based materials and biopolymers in terms of LCA, e.g. ingredients and machineries. Indeed, DF processes are not standard, as manufacturing technologies are often customized depending on use, materials, scale, etc. This means that data must always be adapted to the specific application. Most LCA software does not allow for custom-made database integration, or this operation is extremely labor-intensive. Nonetheless, the use of spreadsheets more easily leads to miscalculations and errors.

3.3 Radicant (single-product assessment)

Radicant is made of 24 custom 3D printed panels based on a bone glue, water, glycerol recipe, with added fiber fillers (wood flour, wood bark, seagrass, cotton bark). All panels have different amount of base mixture and fibers. Every panel consists of 2 layers: the “base” layer uses seagrass or wood flour as filler, in percentage around 15%

per liter; the “leaf” layer uses cotton bark and wood bark as filler, in percentage around 9% per liter. The production process is divided into 3 phases:

1. 24 hours cooking of a mix of bone glue, glycerol and water;
2. Base mixture mixing with filler fibers (20 minutes for 1 liter);
3. 3D printing with a custom-fixed extruder mounted on an universal cobot.

Fig. 2. Radicant material input and output flows map.

Optional phases might involve the use of refrigerator to store the mixture and the bain marie to keep parts at temperature before the mixing process.

The LCA focuses on the panels production, transportation to the site and the whole assembly of the installation (A1-A5).

The LCIA is guided by specific impact-related questions, namely:

- which of the materials from the recipe has the worst environmental score in terms of Global Warming Potential (GWP);
- which of the 24 panels of the Radicant exhibit has the worst environmental score in terms of GWP;
- which process phase has the worst environmental impact in terms of Total use of non-renewable energy as primary resource (PENRT).

Fig. 3. Radicant panel digital fabrication process. Courtesy of CITA.

In A1-A3 LCA modules, all ingredients are mapped and restructured into their production phases (A1). Impacts are collected differently according to the data available for every ingredient. Water and construction materials data (timber sticks, metal fittings, adhesive led stripes) are taken from the ÖKOBAUDAT database (Table 1). All values are converted to the functional unit of 1 kg. In A3, the manufacturing process is analyzed for each panel, specifically for every “base” and “leaf” layers.

Table 1. Ingredients and materials data related to their manufacturing phase (module A1)

Ingredient	Original Functional Unit	Source	Geographical context
Bone glue	1 kg	[20]	N/A
Wood bark	1 m ³	[37]	Serbia
Wood flour	1 lt	[38]	USA
Seagrass	1 kg	[15]	Denmark
Cotton bark	1 m ²	[15]	Denmark
Glycerol	1 kg	[39]	USA
Wood sticks	1kg	[14]	Germany
Metal screws	1 kg	[14]	Germany
Adhesive LED stripes	20 million lumen hrs	[40]	USA

3.4 Rawlam (comparative assessment)

The methodology is tested for the comparative analysis between Glulam data from the ÖKOBAUDAT database and the Rawlam prototype.

The Rawlam manufacturing process is divided into 4 phases:

1. CT scanning of spruce logs to detect wood knots, failures, etc.;
2. logs cutting into lamellas, planing and thicknessing;
3. Glulam pressing and re-planing;
4. boards assembly.

The LCA focuses on the timber beams manufacturing, transportation to the site and the whole assembly of the installation (A1-A5). Since the aim of Rawlam is to optimize timber use in structural components manufacturing processes, LCIA was guided by specific impact-related questions, namely: the total amount of Non-Hazardous Waste Disposed (HWD), Components for Reuse (CRU) and Materials for Recycling (MFR) among phases A2-A3; the total amount of CRU in kg in phase A3 between Glulam and Rawlam; the total amount of MFR in kg in phase A3 between Glulam and Rawlam.

The functional unit for the comparison is 1 kg. According to the assessment's purposes, A1 phase is considered not relevant for the analysis, as wood source for Glulam and Rawlam might be the same.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Radicant

The analysis of materials impact in Radicant helps to spot possible points to improve for environmental impacts reduction. In terms of GWP, animal glue and cotton stand as potential targets for enhancing the sustainability of the recipe.

The comparison between panels in terms of GWP highlights no significant differences in recipes impacts. Nonetheless, panels with wood fibers in both “base” and “leaf” layer as filler fibers demonstrate to have a better environmental score. A1 phase is the most impacting in terms of PENRT. Both transportation phases A2 and A4 have no significant weight on the overall evaluation. Most of energy consumption is thus embodied in material manufacturing, while the exhibition itself has low impact scores.

Fig. 4. GWP (Kg CO₂ eq.) analysis of Radicant panels ingredients considering A1-A3 LCA modules.

To possible guide future printing projects, GWP data for 1 kg are converted to 1 meter of filament. Taking Panel 0 recipe as an example, the “base” layer (8 lt of materials) corresponds to 1.15E-02 kg CO₂ eq. per m. The “leaf” layer (3 lt of materials) corresponds to 2.54E-02 kg CO₂ eq. per m.

4.2 Rawlam

Results from comparing A2-A3 phases between Glulam and Rawlam highlight significant differences in terms of NHWD from transportation in the latter, where logs are imported from Trieste (Italy). This suggests that is best to source wood locally when possible. In A3, Glulam produces more than $5.00E+02$ kg of NHWD, while in Rawlam this is hugely reduced in favor of CRU and MFR. In particular, the Glulam EPD from ÖKOBAUDAT does not report any CRU or MFR amounts.

Fig. 5. Rawlam vs Glulam: LCA analysis for A2-A3 modules in terms of NHWD, CRU and MFR (all expressed in Kg.).

4.3 Sensitivity Analysis

To deal with the data uncertainty and provide for reliable results, for both Radicant and Rawlam assessment a Sensitivity Analysis is performed. This allows to understand the impact variation due to possible errors or ambiguity across individual components of the structures (i.e. panels for Radicant, boards for RawLam).

Fig. 6. GWP variation accross panels

In the first case, the analysis focuses first on the GWP scores of the various panels, as shown in Figure 6. While panels 1 and 16 display higher emissions due to their larger size (twice the dimensions of the other panels), panel 21 displays lower emissions due to the higher proportion of wood flour in the recipe (12.7%).

Other panels display similar GWP scores ($2.56E+01$ min., $2.77E+01$ max., considering same-size panels). The 24 panels use 20 different recipes, and the study of their GWP scores therefore also provide data for a sensitivity analysis of the recipe's materials quantities. Figure 7 displays the highest and lowest percentages of material quantities and of CO₂ emissions across all panels and recipes. It highlights which material has the largest influence over GWP variations when modifying the recipes. Bark and wood flour have the lowest impacts in comparison to material amounts, which informs further the low GWP score of panel 21. Cotton and glue display the highest impacts compared to material amount, and in particular the latter would be an ingredient to focus on in further material research.

Fig. 7. Recipe variation sensitivity analysis. % of recipe (blue) vs % of CO₂ emissions (red).

In the second case, the sensitivity analysis focused on CRU and MFR scores of the different boards, as shown in Figure 8. NHWD was not considered in the sensitivity analysis as the waste in this category originates in the fabrication process, not the boards themselves. This allows for a best- and worst-case scenario analysis, in which the amount of reusable/recyclable materials vary depending on the quality of the logs.

Fig. 8. Impact variation across Rawlam boards

5 Conclusions

In this paper, the challenge of a LCA analysis of environmental sustainability of digital fabrication with bio-based materials in research stage is addressed by designing and testing a LCA-oriented methodology. This study is performed as an ex-post analysis on two different prototyped realized and exhibited by CITA, i.e. Radicant and Rawlam. In both cases, opportunities and limitations of the application of LCA to experimental practices for ecological alternatives in construction are exposed.

The limitations we encountered are mostly in terms of lack of data and uncertainty. To address these problems, we perform a Sensitivity Analysis, examining the range of errors and impact scenarios in both assessments, so to improve the reliability of results to inform a decision-making process.

Further developments of this study will focus on direct acquisition of data from manufactures. Also, a better connection between the spreadsheet and the design software (i.e. Rhinoceros/Grasshopper) might indeed help LCA to become a proper decision support system. Eventually, a comparison between ex-post and during-development data might highlight significative changes in the results.

Finally, LCA allows for deeper reflections on sustainability of DF and questions the upscale and replication of experimental manufacturing research projects in different contexts. If applied at the very early stage of the process, LCA can serve as a design and research decision support system in the laboratory.

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